

Christendom Witnesses to the Martyrs: Modulations of the Acta Martyrum in Prudentius'
Peristephanon, vi

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In hymn vi of his Peristephanon, Prudentius dramatically reworks the plot of Passio Fructuosi. The poet turns the perpetrators from well-known and dutiful representatives of a transient empire into despicable caricatures of evil and vice, transforms the martyred bishop from a caring pastor into a heroic leader of heroes, re-narrates the roles of Christian family members as anonymous martyr-cult devotees, and shifts the focus from the martyred bishop as a local, beloved model of imitation and encouragement during a time of persecution to the three martyrs together as co-equal objects of worship and patrons and saviours of their region and devotees.

If early martyr stories are the beating heart of proto-Orthodox piety, then Orthodoxy's ongoing vitality may well pulse in the later renditions of those very stories, in their shifting cadences and tones. As F. J. E. Raby maintained, '[t]he new conception of the martyr, which was to dominate the whole middle ages, was the creation of the post-Constantinian Church'.¹ Listening to the ways in which a particular example of this 'new conception' differs from its pre-Constantinian

AC= *Acts of St. Cyprian*; CCSL= Corpus Christianorum series latina; CSEL= Corpus Scriptorum Ecclesiasticorum Latinorum; LCL=Loeb Classical Library; *Pionius*= *Martyrdom of Pionius*; *Polycarp*= *Martyrdom of Polycarp*; PF= *Passio Fructuosi*; *Peristephanon*= Prudentius, *Peristephanon*

The critical edition used in this article is *Aurelii Prudentii Clementis Carmina*, ed. Johan Bergman, CSEL lxi, Vienna-Leipzig 1926. Occasionally referenced is *Aurelii Prudentii Clementis Carmina*, ed. Maurice Cunningham, CCSL cxxvi, Turnholt 1966. Thomson's English translation is also occasionally referenced: *Prudentius ii*, ed. H. J. Thomson, LCL ccxcviii, Cambridge 1953. Other martyr texts referenced are mostly found in *The acts of the Christian martyrs*, ed. Herbert Musurillo, Oxford 1972.

¹ F. J. E. Raby, *A history of Christian Latin poetry from the beginnings to the close of the Middle Ages*, Oxford 1953, ii. 51.

counterpart should prove a useful exercise in tracing out modulations in Christianity and its relationships to broader society.

Eusebius of Caesarea, both in his *Collection of ancient martyrdoms* and *Ecclesiastical history*, presents the earliest subject matter for such a project. He explicitly recounts pre-Constantinian martyr accounts, yet places them in the context of post-Constantinian reappraisals of the role of the martyrs. In his life and literature, Eusebius simultaneously reflects the experiences, perspectives and concerns of two eras, that of the great persecutor Diocletian and that of Constantine, his friend and patron, and a ‘savior for all’.²

Transformations to earlier stories become even more striking as time passes and Orthodoxy comes into clearer relief. Of particular note here is the poesis of Prudentius in his martyr-compendium, the *Peristephanon*, or *Martyr’s crown*. Not all of *Peristephanon* is suitable for such an inquiry, both because Prudentius did not always closely attend to written sources and because some of those he did use have disappeared. Of the sources he did use, the one he most closely reproduces is clearly the *Passion of Fructuosus, Augurius and Eulogius* in *Peristephanon* vi.³ His careful reading and recapitulation of the details of this account probably stem in part from his considerable pride for the pious ancestors of his native Hispania Tarraconensis,⁴ as well as the familiarity of the text by virtue of its presence in the liturgy of the martyrs’ dies natalis. Yet, even while faithful to this text beyond all others, he alters it in manifold ways in his poetic retelling. Scholars have previously noted many of the similarities and differences between Prudentius and his source here.⁵ However, most of these treatments have not offered a sustained

² *Ecclesiastical history* x.8.18.

³ The next closest is *Peristephanon*, xiii, based in part on AC, to which Prudentius adds at least two other less reliable traditions, both of which are actually unrelated to the martyrdom: see Anne-Marie Palmer, *Prudentius on the martyrs*, Oxford-New York 1989, 235-6. See also John Petruccione, ‘Prudentius’ portrait of St. Cyprian: an idealized biography’, *Revue des études augustinienes* xxxvi (1990), 225-41; P. Tino Alberto Sabbatini, ‘Storia e leggenda nei *Peristephanon* di Prudenzio I,’ *Revista di studi classici* (1972), 47-53.

⁴ Scholars concur that Prudentius hailed from this province. The precise city provokes debate. Palmer and Roberts are convinced about Calahorra (Callaguris): see Palmer, *Prudentius*, 21, and Michael John Roberts, *Poetry and the cult of the martyrs: the liber Peristephanon of Prudentius*, Ann Arbor 1993, 1. Bergman and Thomson favor Saragossa (Caesaraugusta): see CSEL lxi pp. ix-x and LCL cccxcviii p. vii. In *Peristephanon* self-involved language is applied to cities throughout Tarraconensis. Given the plurality of evidence, the positions taken in the debate about his hometown seem a bit too certain. What emerges clearly is that the poet’s literary persona is at home in the entire province. Even the hymns to Roman martyrs read as pilgrimage journey narrative and summons for adopting Roman martyr-cults throughout Tarraconensis.

⁵ For example, Palmer, *Prudentius*, ch vii; Roberts, *Poetry*, passim; Sabbatini, ‘Storia e leggenda’, 37-43; P. Franchi de’ Cavalieri, ‘Gli atti di S. Fruttuoso di Tarragona’, in *Note*

comparative analysis and have only passingly addressed how the cumulative differences illustrate broader changes in Christianity and its relationships to society.

PF and *Peristephanon* vi obviously come from different periods and contexts. With certain caveats, *PF* dates to the late third or early fourth century.⁶ While reflective of hagiographical legend, the account does offer a plausible setting for the martyrdom. The bishop Fructuosus and his two deacons, Augurius and Eulogius, suffered death by fire in the Roman-Spanish city of Tarragona (or Tarraco) on 21 January 259.⁷ Following the edict of emperor Valerian,⁸ co-sponsored by co-emperor Gallienus, the local sentence of execution was passed by Aemilianus,

agiografiche viii (Studi e Testi lxxv, 1935), 136ff. Malamud ignores *Peristephanon*, vi. in her analysis of the poetics of martyrdom in *Peristephanon*: see Martha A. Malamud, *A poetics of transformation: Prudentius and classical mythology*, Ithaca 1989.

⁶ In regard to *PF*, i-iv, Musurillo grants a terminus ad quem as late as c. 313 but favors an earlier date: see *Acts*, p. xxxii. He attributes v-vii to a 'later, more pious hand', though how late he does not say: *ibid.* In the footnotes Musurillo avers that Prudentius does refer to content in *PF*, v: *ibid.* 183 n. 13. He follows de' Cavalieri by absenting from the main text a long legend about Fructuosus appearing to believers to have his martyrs remains gathered under the altar: *ibid.* 182 n 21; cf. de' Cavalieri, 'Gli atti', 163. Whether Prudentius knows this legend seems quite debatable, but the analysis below will presume de' Cavalieri's conclusion here. Regarding *PF*, vii, Musurillo sympathetically alludes to Alonso's theory of a fifth century interpolation: cf. *Acts*, 185 n 16 and J. Fernández Alonso, 'Fruttuoso, vescore di Tarragona, Augurio ed Eulogio, diaconi, santi, martiri', in *Bibliotheca sanctorum* (Rome 1964), v. 1297. Musurillo's general assessment represents something of a consensus in recent decades: see Sabbatini, 'Storia e leggenda', 37-8; Jill Harries, 'Review of Anne-Marie Palmer, *Prudentius on the martyrs*', *The Classical Review* ns. xl (1990), 39; Christopher J. Haas, 'Imperial religious policy and Valerian's persecution of the church, a.d. 257-260', *Church History* lii (1983), 140 n. 39; Paul Keresztes, 'Two edicts of the Emperor Valerian', *Vigiliae Christianae* xxix (1975), 85 n. 36; Manjarrés Mangas and Roldán Hervás, *España Romana (218 a. de J.C.-414 de J.C.): la sociedad, el derecho, la cultura*, Madrid 1982, ii 416-7; Palmer, *Prudentius*, 207-8.

⁷ Palmer, *Prudentius*, 21; Musurillo, *Acts*, p. xxxii. *PF* notes how this happened 'die dominica': i.1. The reference to the Lord's Day stands in the tradition of *Polycarp*, xxi, *Pionius*, xxiii and *Martyrdom of Apollonius*, xlvii, which very intentionally make reference to the dominion of Christ when dating the events. See also 'the Eternal King': *Polycarp* xxiii. Such references demonstrated a 'scorn for the temporal sub specie aeternitatis': see Herbert B. Workmann, *Persecution in the early church*, Oxford 1980, 41. Such a defiant reference may have been even more poignant if the Lord's Day happened to coincide with a major pagan festival, as Robin Lane Fox argues of *Polycarp*: see *Pagans and Christians*, New York 1987, 485.

⁸ This ordered 'all those who do not practice Roman beliefs to acknowledge the Roman rites': *AC* i.1; see Musurillo, *Acts*, 169.

proconsul of Hispania citerior.⁹ Whether written during the reign of Valerian or Diocletian, the early martyr-story came into being in or near a time of heated persecution, when Christians in a precarious situation looked for help from sympathetic Romans and courageous guidance from their local leaders. In terms of literary history, this Spanish martyr-passion has many precedents in the Christian martyr stories of the second and third century. The analysis below will point to numerous parallels, particularly in the notes.

The second text, hymn vi of *Peristephanon*, dates to around the turn of the fifth century.¹⁰ Thus it belongs to a singular moment of Western Christian optimism in the wake of Theodosius I and his promulgation of *Cunctos populos*, yet undisturbed by the soon-coming barbarian victories within Gaul, Italy, and Spain. This creative moment in the formation of Christendom in the West was exemplified and shaped in many ways by the papal career of Damasus.

It was his Orthodoxy, that of the Roman See in tandem with Alexandria, that Theodosius had promulgated in *Cunctos populos*. While fighting against Arianism among other heresies, and advocating for Rome's political-religious centrality, Damasus proved himself an avid promoter and stern administrator of Rome's martyr cults, financially, architecturally and literarily. He took control of Rome's many catacombs, completely remodeling them. He established and embellished martyr shrines and opened the spaces to accommodate a burgeoning influx of pilgrims. In the process he dramatically shifted the gender balance of Rome's martyr cults.¹¹ In his own house he had a titular basilica built and consecrated to St. Lawrence, whose military career and martyrdom represented Rome's conquest by Christ. In honor of various Roman martyrs he even composed his own *Epigrams*, which were soon impressed upon many of Rome's martyr shrines and walls, inscribed in a unique style by the expert hand of Furius Dionysius Philocalus.

⁹ Musurillo, *Acts*, 179 n. 1.

¹⁰ Quasten puts hymns i-vii prior to his journey to Rome around AD 401-3: see Johannes Quasten, *Patrology*, Westminster-Utrecht 1986, iv. 281, 293-4.

¹¹ Nicola Denzey has shown convincingly that Damasus devoted to male martyr patronage many sites traditionally associated with female martyrs. The few sanctioned female cults that remained exemplified the virtue of virginity: see Denzey, *The bone gatherers: the lost worlds of early Christian women*, Boston 2007, ch vii. Prudentius' martyr compendium seems to mirror these reforms. The stories are predominantly about men, while the two female accounts are expressly dedicated to 'virgin' martyrs, respectively Eulalia and Agnes: see *Peristephanon*, iii. line 3 and *Peristephanon*, xiv. line 4. Seen as a whole, the *Peristephanon* seems to echo Rome's promulgation of a virgin martyr, Agnes, with an Iberian counterpart in Eulalia. Prudentius even makes this Lusitanian an anonymous adoptee of Caesaraugusta in Tarraconensis: *Peristephanon*, iv. lines 177-8.

Damasus died in 384, perhaps about the time when the literary career of Prudentius began to flourish.¹² As a pilgrim to Rome, Prudentius directly participated in Damasus' unified system of martyr-cultus. This Roman experience and vision saturates the work of Prudentius, as the analysis below will show. Occasional references to the *Epigrams* even appear in the *Peristephanon*.¹³ Thus Damasus set the stage for the involved poesis of one of Western empire's first Christian civic poets. Yet, as the Pope's brief verses only touch upon traditional texts, the poet's stand out in the way he reflects and transforms earlier texts and traditions, especially that of Fructuosus.

Prudentius' reliance on and modifications to *PF* are evident from the outset even in the title. The shift from 'sanctorum' to 'beatissimorum' serves to evoke honorific reverence for the sainted martyrs, while the addition of the church's name and location serves to highlight the place of the martyrdom and the martyrs' shrine.¹⁴ How else does Prudentius modify the previous account, especially as it redounds to the perceived relationship between Church and Empire?

Numerous examples show that Prudentius turns the perpetrators from known, duty-bound representatives of a transient empire and potential sympathizers into generic yet despicable caricatures of evil and vice. At the beginning of the original story, the group of six, specifically named 'beneficiarii'¹⁵ demonstrate kindness and patience by allowing the bishop to put on his

¹² T. D. Barnes and R. W. Westall, 'The Conversion of the Roman Aristocracy in Prudentius' *Contra Symmachum* *Phoenix* xlv (1991), 61, raises the possibility for a date as early as 384 for that text.

¹³ See Sabbatini, 'Storia e leggenda', 34-5.

¹⁴ Cf. *Peristephanon*, vi, title, and *PF*, title. All Latin quotations from *PF* are taken from Musurillo, *Acts*, 176-84, and follow chapter and subsection format. All Latin quotations from Prudentius are taken from Bergman's CSEL lxi, and follow book and line format. For a discussion of the widespread scrutiny of Cunningham's text in CCSL cxxvi, see A. A. R. Bastiaensen, 'Prudentius in recent literary criticism', in Jan den Boeft and Anthony Hilhorst (eds), *Early Christian poetry: a collection of essays*, Leiden-New York 1993, 101ff. Even so, in the main text at hand, Cunningham's edition only varies from Bergman's in three places, two of which are of little consequence. The first is a spelling variant in line 61 in which Cunningham opts for 'rotunda' over 'rutunda': cf. CCSL cxxvi. 316 and CSEL lxi. 357. Second, Cunningham favors 'tunc' instead of 'tum' in line 127: cf. CCSL cxxvi. 319 and CSEL lxi. 360. Finally, in the title Cunningham opts for the lesser represented mss tradition of removing the place name and the reference to the deacons, 'ECCLESIAE TARRACONENSIS, ET... DIACONORUM': cf. CCSL cxxvi. 314 and CSEL lxi. 355. Their inclusion certainly fits the poem's emphasis, as this analysis will show. All English translations of *PF* and *Peristephanon*, vi are this author's.

¹⁵ 'privileged soldiers', 'bodyguards', or 'orderlies', namely, 'Aurelius, Festicius, Aelius, Pollentius, Donatus, et Maximus': *PF*, i.2.

sandals, only then leading him to the agora.¹⁶ But in *Peristephanon*, they contort into a single, beastly ‘pastus sanguine carnifex’.¹⁷ The protagonist who in *PF* prays unceasingly in prison, ‘certus et gaudens de corona domini’,¹⁸ in *Peristephanon* informs his jailed companions that these events portend the conspiracy of a ‘cruentus... coluber’,¹⁹ that is, Satan. When the interrogation begins in *PF*, the proconsul Aemilianus simply asks the accused, ‘audisti quid imperatores praceperunt’?²⁰ In *Peristephanon*, however, the demonised judge demands the worship of demons: ‘iudex Aemilianus inminebat / atrox, turbidus, insolens, profanus; / aras daemonicas coli iubebat’.²¹

The differing responses of Fructuosus to this inquiry provide further evidence. In the earlier account, he defiantly responds that he does not recognize the imperial commands nor the gods whom they reference; rather he seditiously confesses himself a Christian.²² In *Peristephanon* the martyr-to-be does not expose Rome herself, but rather the co-emperor’s hubris, pointing out an all-important theological gap, ‘factorem dominumque Gallieni’.²³ The proconsul’s altered response complements the picture. Both accounts recall his acerbic jibe about the termination of the bishop’s vocation, ‘fuisti’, along with the sentence of being burned alive.²⁴ But while the

¹⁶ *Ibid.* i.3.

¹⁷ ‘Blood-fed executioner’: *Peristephanon*, vi. line 17. The topos of the executioner as a wild and hungry animal occurs throughout *Peristephanon*: see iii. line 87; v. lines 152, 331. Roberts notes its previous use, citing Silius vi.531 and 4 Macc. ix.28, xii.13: see *Poetry*, 65 n. 66.

¹⁸ *PF*, vi.4.

¹⁹ *Peristephanon*, vi. lines 22-3. This may evoke Job xxvi.13, which says, in reference to El’s killing of Leviathan in creation, ‘manu eius eductus est coluber tortuosus’. *Martyrs of Lyons* i.42 speaks similarly of the fragile martyr Blandina as gaining victory over ‘the crooked serpent’.

²⁰ *PF*, ii.2.

²¹ *Peristephanon*, vi. lines 34-6, demonised with asyndeton: ‘The judge Aemilianus was threatening / —the cruel, the frantic, the arrogant, the profane—, / was ordering [them] to worship at demonic altars’.

²² ‘nescio quid praeceperunt’: *PF*, ii.3. This is not in the sense of sheer ignorance of the well-known decree of Gallienus to worship the numina, but rather of obstinate defiance, a refusal to recognize imperial authority. ‘nescio,’ responding to the question, ‘scis esse deos?’ conveys the same lack of respect and recognition: *ibid.* 2.5. ‘ego Christianus sum’ echoes a topos of defiance that runs across early martyria: cf. *ibid.* 2.4; *Polycarp*, x; *Martyrdom of Carpus, Papyrus and Agathonice*, v, xxii, xxxiv; *Martyrdom of Justin and Companions*, iii.4, iv.1-6; iv.9; *Martyrs of Lyons*, i.19, 20; *Acts of the Scillitan Martyrs*, ix-x, xiii; *Martyrdom of Apollonius*, ii; *Passion of Perpetua*, iii.2, vi.4; *Pionius*, vii.5, viii.2, ix.5, xv.2; *AC*, ii.

²³ *Peristephanon*, vi. line 45.

²⁴ Cf. *PF*, ii.9, ‘fuisti’ and *Peristephanon*, vi. line 48, ‘iam fuisti’.

older account records that sentence nonchalantly,²⁵ Prudentius reads it as the official's own sadistic choice, illustrative of a vicious psyche brimming over with fury, 'he does not defer rage or restrain anger / [but] sends them to be cremated in cruel blazes'.²⁶

Regarding the execution of the sentence, while *PF* remains silent as to how the fires are kindled, Prudentius points to a diabolical agent, a 'dark officer'.²⁷ Both compare the martyr company to the companions of Daniel,²⁸ but Prudentius extends the metaphor to identify Aemilianus with Nebuchadnezzar, that 'Babylonicum... tremens tyrannus'.²⁹ *PF* also explains that as Fructuosus and his deacons are escorted to the 'amphitheatre', 'populus Fructuosum episcopum dolere coepit quia talem amorem habebat non tantum a fratribus sed etiam ab ethnicis'.³⁰ But Prudentius makes no room for sympathetic outsiders. Instead, he focuses in on the mere mention of the

²⁵ 'et iussit eos vivos ardere': *PF*, ii.9. The tone here suggests that being burned alive was not expressive of special malice, but rather common in the execution of Christians, which other evidence confirms: cf. *Polycarp xv, Martyrdom of Carpus, Papyrus and Agathonice xxxvi and ff.*; *Pionius xx*. Musurillo, *Acts*, p. lii, absents *PF* from those acta demonstrating 'special cruelty' by the soldiers or prison guards. Cremation could also serve as an intentional strategy to curb the would-be cult of the martyr, perceived as a potentially seditious alternative to emperor worship: see *Martyrs of Lyons i.61-3*.

²⁶ 'nec differt furor aut refrenat iram, / saevis destinat ignis cremandos': *Peristephanon*, vi. lines 49-50. Ira takes over the proconcul's character. Ira characterizes the presiding officials throughout Prudentius' writings: see *Cathemerinon*, xii. lines 109-10 (Herod's slaughter of innocents) and *Peristephanon*, x. lines 111, 547 (Asclepiades' execution of Romanus). Jan den Boeft and Jan Bremmer note how early Christian martyr stories consistently have Christians on the receiving end of accusations of rage and madness, rather than the Roman officials deciding their cases: 'Notiunculae martyrologicae', *Vigiliae Christianae xxxv* (1981), 45. They cite, among others: *Acts of the Scillitan Martyrs*, i, viii; *AC*, iv.1; *Martyrdom of Agapes*, iii.7, iv.2, v.1; *Pionius*, xx.2- 3; *Passion of Saint Irenaeus*, iii.4; *Acts of Euplus*, ii.3. Pliny's *Ep.* x.96.4 shows the same, as do 4 Macc. viii.5, x.13 and Acts xxvi.24. Prudentius reverses the traditional script and thus illustrates Christian triumph in a contest of virtue.

²⁷ 'niger minister': *Peristephanon*, vi. line 67.

²⁸ *PF*, iv.2. Daniel's companions are pictured as martyrs elsewhere in early Christian and Jewish literature: see, for example, Hilary, *Trinity* x.45; Augustine, *Epistles* clxxxv.8; 4 Mac. xvi; *Gen.Rab.* xxxiv.13; *b. Taan.* fo. 18b (told by Trajan!).

²⁹ *Peristephanon*, vi. lines 109-11. Prudentius pictures the three companions of Daniel, and the three martyrs like them, 'cantantes' in the fire, participating in the heavenly liturgy at the moment of fiery disaster: see *Peristephanon*, vi. lines 110-11; also *Apotheosis*, lines 147-52. Prudentius envisions the devil himself as a 'tyrant' 'who has usurped the rule of man from God and control of the world from man': see John Petruccione, 'The persecutor's envy and the rise of the martyr cult: *Peristephanon* hymns 1 and 4', *Vigiliae Christianae* xlv (1991), 333.

³⁰ *PF*, iii.1.

amphitheatre and re-imagines it a frenzied mob seething around a spectacle, a place ‘madens ferarum / multo sanguine quem furor frequentat’,³¹ along with roars of delight as would resound over a gladiatorial contest.³² Prudentius also leaves out the reference to a Christian soldier named Felix and his supplication, while still paraphrasing Fructuosus’ response.³³ He also absents the carefully constructed reference to Fructuosus preaching even to the same ‘beneficiariis quorum nomina supra memoravimus’.³⁴ Where the *Passio* looked for sympathy and appealed to justice, Prudentius finds only unrestrained malevolence.

After the execution, in *PF* two male Christian³⁵ attendants from the proconsul’s household, along with Aemilianus’ daughter, see the heavens opened and the three martyrs rising. Though they point this out to the governor, ‘videre eos non fuit dignus’.³⁶ But in *Peristephanon*, only one unidentified attendant of the governor,³⁷ along with the governor’s ‘virgin’ daughter,³⁸ witness the miraculous flight, in contrast to the ‘blind parent, so that the household was terrified because of the house-master’s guilt’.³⁹ A new distinction emerges, not one between insider and outsider revelation, but rather between the optics of virtue and vice.⁴⁰ In sum, participants and

³¹ *Peristephanon*, vi. lines 62-3.

³² *Ibid.* lines 64-6.

³³ Cf. *Peristephanon*, vi. line 84 and *PF*, iii.5-6. The older likely echoes the sympathetic, converted soldiers in Mark xv 39, Matt. xxvii 54, and Luke xxiii 47.

³⁴ *PF*, iv.1. Fructuosus apparently reciprocates the kindness shown at his arrest, including them proleptically in his flock, leading even his executioners to salvation.

³⁵ ‘Babyla et Mygdonio fratres nostri ex familia Aemiliani’: *ibid.* v.1. Franchi de’ Cavalieri, favors the variant ‘Babylon’ over ‘Babyla’: ‘Gli atti’, 191. Boeft and Bremer follow suit, sharply dissecting Musurillo’s text at this point: ‘Notinulae’, 51.

³⁶ *PF*, v.2.

³⁷ ‘praesidis ex domo satellites’: *Peristephanon*, vi. line 121.

³⁸ ‘haec tum virginitas palam videre / per sudum meruit’: *ibid.* lines 127-8.

³⁹ ‘parente caeco, / ut crimen domini domus timeret’: *ibid.* lines 128-9.

⁴⁰ At the end of the *Passio*, the three martyrs appear to Aemelianus in order to rebuke the proconsul and vindicate themselves: *PF*, vii.1. Scholars have debated whether this part dates to before or after Prudentius; see above. Some parallels may suggest dependence and thus a date before Prudentius. ‘Fructuosus pariter cum diaconibus’ appeared to rebuke Aemelianus: *PF*, vii.1. ‘pariter’ may have evoked Prudentius’ word choice near poem’s end, ‘reddamus paribus pares camenas’: *Peristephanon*, vi. line 153. An overt Trinitarian benediction closes the source: *PF*, vii.2. The poem’s conclusion may respond antiphonally, ‘triplex’ and ‘triforme’: *Peristephanon*, vi. line 142. Also, the latter may mirror the former in the concluding shift of focus to the martyrs as a group, and their direct invocation: *PF*, vii.2 repeats ‘o beati martyres’ twice. *Peristephanon*, vi. lines 142-4 invokes them as a group, then proceeds to participate in their congregational veneration in lines 145-62. If Prudentius knew of the appearance to Aemilianus, the poet had ample reason to omit it intentionally. It contradicted itself within the

functionaries that distract from caricature are removed; those remaining are consolidated and recast as personifications of evil and vice.

Prudentius also transforms the martyred bishop from a loving pastor into a heroic leader of heroes. While he does keep the standard title of martyrs for the three,⁴¹ Prudentius also unabashedly deploys ‘vir’ in the Vergilian sense. Augustine conscientiously avoided this connotation, since he perceived the Christian life and the ideal of heroism as fundamentally incompatible.⁴² Thus in *Peristephanon* Fructuosus gives the battle cry to his companions: ‘mecum state, viri’.⁴³ In stark contrast, *PF* nowhere names a ‘vir’, speaking simply of Fructuosus as a ‘beatus martyr’,⁴⁴ and otherwise as a shepherd (‘pastor’)⁴⁵ whose actions in his martyrdom reflect not heroism as much as love for God⁴⁶ and fatherly love for his ecclesial children.⁴⁷ Only once and briefly does Prudentius have Fructuosus speak of his episcopal vocation as ‘famulus gregisque pastor’.⁴⁸ Otherwise, only official⁴⁹ and heroic descriptors apply. Both draw a parallel between the bishop’s and Christ’s refusal of wine, but whereas the first has the bishop look forward to breaking fast at the eschatological feast of the faithful, the second focuses on his exacting self-denial.⁵⁰ After the execution in *Peristephanon*, the proconsul’s attendant beholds the martyrs as ‘insignesque viros’, being ushered into heaven and through the stars.⁵¹ At the close of the poem, Prudentius also addresses various groups within the congregation who sing

source, and it ran counter to the poet’s caricature of guilty blindness. The evidence simply does not allow for certainty on this point, however.

⁴¹ *Peristephanon*, vi. line 6.

⁴² Robert Louis Wilken, *The spirit of early Christian thought*, New Haven 2003, 224, citing *de Civitate dei* x.21.

⁴³ ‘Stand with me, heroes’: *Peristephanon*, vi. line 22.

⁴⁴ *PF*, iii.5. Fructuosus and his deacons are addressed as ‘beati martyres’: *ibid.* vii.2.

Elsewhere he is simply ‘Fructuosum martyrem’: *ibid.* vi.3.

⁴⁵ *Ibid.* vi.1.

⁴⁶ Implicitly in the quotation of 1 Cor. ii.9: *ibid.* iii.3. Breaking the fast ‘martyribus et prophetis in paradiso’ also motivates the bishop: *ibid.*

⁴⁷ iv.1. See also how Fructuosus addresses the eager Augustalis as ‘fili’: *ibid.* iii.5

⁴⁸ *Peristephanon*, vi. line 47.

⁴⁹ The designation of ‘priest’, see *Peristephanon*, vi. lines 14, 43, 52, occurs most, followed by ‘bishop’: *Peristephanon*, vi. line 11.

⁵⁰ Cf. *PF*, iii.2-3 and *Peristephanon*, vi. lines 52-60.

⁵¹ ‘caelum martyribus patere apertum / insignesque viros per astra ferri’: *Peristephanon*, vi. lines 122-3. ‘[P]er astra’ may allude to Statius, who describes the flight of birds ‘per astra’, ‘through the skies’: Statius i.6.75 and iv.3.38. The phrase signifies post-mortem deification for Prudentius. He also uses the phrase, probably at least partially as a reference to his own poetic and mnemonic technique, to describe the geographical flights possible only by the mind and soul: *Hamartigenia* line 895.

the martyr hymn of the dies natalis, including a certain category of persons named ‘heros’. This apparently references a group of male ascetics who stand as counterparts to female ascetics, who are collectively called ‘virgo’.⁵² Apparently even a segment of the bardic choir may become heroes by participation.

Key to this character shift is how the miraculous, while present in *PF*, superabounds in Prudentius' retelling. Both accounts record six days in prison and a baptism there. But while *PF* says Fructuosus enacts the initiation, *Peristephanon* has the three ‘perform the mystical bath’, and the result is a luminous victory that baffles darkness itself.⁵³ Both accounts mention that Fructuosus opts to remove his sandals prior to his execution.⁵⁴ But only *Peristephanon* points to the otherworldly courage involved, that Fructuosus did this in order to place his feet more quickly in the fire,⁵⁵ drawing near to God in a deed akin to Moses himself,⁵⁶ while all three martyrs enter the fire ‘rapidis... passibus’.⁵⁷ Before this happens, in *PF* Fructuosus gives a brief yet inspired homily aimed at consoling his people’s grief and turning their trust to divine promises.⁵⁸ Yet in *Peristephanon*, the martyr's last loving sermon becomes an oracle in which a

⁵² *Peristephanon*, vi. line 149. Thomson translates ‘heros’ as ‘grown men’: LCL cccxcviii.212. Prudentius uses the term in a wide variety of applications, for example, of John the Evangelist/Revelator for his mental flight, *Cathemerinon*, vi lines 113-6, probably understood by Prudentius as parallel to his own inspired, hymnic geography; of Tobit for his burial (martyr-cult) piety, *Cathemerinon*, x. lines 69-76; and of Romanus for his calm during torture, *Peristephanon*, x. lines 455-6. But none justify Thomson’s translation here. The *Oxford Latin Dictionary* and *Oxford Classical Dictionary* entries also mention no such connotation in classical literature. Thomson also translates ‘virgo’ as ‘girls’: *ibid.* In the ecclesial context, and given Prudentius' own ascetic discipline of fasting during the day, this first pairing of adjacent identifiers, ‘heros’ / ‘virgo’, probably does not merely point contrastingly to male and female, but also identifies them as ascetics, and thus also as heroes of the faith. The next grouping draws a similar pair of opposites, ‘puer’ / ‘senex’.

⁵³ *Peristephanon*, vi. lines 29-30, ‘exercent ibi mysticum lavacrum,/et purgamen aquae stupent tenebrae’. Palmer notes the miraculous connotation of ‘mysticum’: *Prudentius*, 213.

⁵⁴ Likely an omage to Polycarp, which in turn mirrors Moses in Exod. iii.5: *Polycarp*, xiii.

⁵⁵ ‘atquin ipse meos pedes resolvam, / ne vestigia praepedita vinclis / tardis gressibus inruant in ignem’: *Peristephanon*, vi. lines 79-81.

⁵⁶ Prudentius explicitly likens him to Moses entering the presence of God: *Peristephanon*, vi. lines 85-90. The Passion perhaps hints at this motif, calling close attention to the removal of sandals as a would-be martyr relic, but does not make the Moses comparison explicit: *PF*, i.3, iii.4. Prudentius also intertextually re-narrates the story of Moses as a would-be martyr contest. Moses takes off his sandals en route to Pharaoh’s court in *Dittochaeon*, viii line 32, ‘solvit vincla pedum; properat Pharaonis ad arcem’.

⁵⁷ *Peristephanon*, vi. lines 100-1.

⁵⁸ *PF*, iv.1-2.

spirit sounds directly from heaven, not as a dove but in a portent that makes all present tremble. It assures that victory belongs to the martyrs, whose dying procession takes them into the realm of the ‘Thunderer’, ‘Tonantis’.⁵⁹ Once the fire begins, both accounts point to the parallel between this trio and Ananias, Azariah, and Mishael of Danielic fame.⁶⁰ Yet, Prudentius turns the allusion, a *minori ad maius*, into a case for miraculous courage: while the ‘pious flame spared’⁶¹ the readied, ancient trio, the Spanish martyrs eagerly ‘pray the quick flame to fly upon [them]’.⁶² While both accounts relate how the fire burned the bindings off their hands, Prudentius adds the striking detail that this happened ‘intacta cute’.⁶³ He everywhere elaborates and augments the miraculous, shifting the focus from the bishop as loving pastor to a heroic leader of heroes.

The heroic drama also re-casts noted members of the bishop’s ecclesial family into anonymous martyr-cult devotees. In *PF*, the local church itself is identified as a ‘fraternitas’,⁶⁴ a term absented from *Peristephanon*. Again in *PF*, Rogatianus and Felix are each called ‘our brother’,

⁵⁹ *Peristephanon*, vi. lines 91-9. The reference to a spirit and voice from heaven combines the baptism of Jesus, Mark i 10-11 // Matt. iii 16-7 // Luke iii 22, with a common topos in Homer and his heirs, for example, *Iliad*, viii. lines 169-71, where a three-fold thunderclap of Zeus marks the turning of the battle tide. Prudentius elsewhere employs this common Latinized title for Zeus as a name for the Christian God, *Hamartigenia* line 669, and for Christ as the Thunderer’s Son, *Cathemerinon*, xii lines 81-4 and *Apotheosis* line 171. Thomson passingly notes this as a crass sort of imitation: LCL ccclxxxvii.ix. However, Prudentius had worked through a Biblical and theological rationale for even this *omage* that verges on syncretism. In *Apotheosis*, lines 313-20, Prudentius explicitly ties the divine title to the Father and the Son in connection to Gen. xix 24, which has an odd repetition of the divine name, present in MT, LXX and Vulgate. That ‘Dominus pluit super Sodomam et Gomorram sulphur et ignem a Domino de caelo’ reveals not only that the Jewish-Christian God wields the weapons of Zeus, but also that a certain doubling applies to the inner life of God. Given that Prudentius also uses *Tonans* pejoratively of pagan religion elsewhere—see *Peristephanon*, x. lines 222, 277—, the combined evidence suggests that his overall usage was more careful than crass. If Prudentius has the intertext of Gen. xix 24 in mind here, ‘Tonantis’ evokes divine judgement and victory over the evil persecutors of the faithful.

⁶⁰ *Peristephanon*, vi. lines 109-14 and *PF*, iv.2. *PF* actually uses their Hebrew names here. Incidentally, the Hebrew names do appear in Daniel 1-2, but not Daniel 3, the story recounted here. In that chapter, the Babylonian names are given, both in the MT and LXX. *Peristephanon* papers over the issue, augmenting the list of anonyms elaborated below with these figures well-known to popular Christian memory.

⁶¹ *Peristephanon*, vi. line 112, ‘illis sed pia flamma tunc pepercit’.

⁶² ‘orant, ut celer ignis advolaret’: *ibid.* line 116.

⁶³ *Ibid.* line 105. This miracle allows the martyrs to assume the orans posture.

⁶⁴ *PF*, i.4, one that ‘refreshes’ their bishop: ‘refrigerans’. Prudentius’ bishop would seem to be beyond receiving human help.

and Augustalis the bishop's 'lector'.⁶⁵ In *Peristephanon* these three persons become twoonyms, identified merely by what Fructuosus does for them: one baptised in prison, and the other denied the opportunity to remove the bishop's sandals and refused special favor in view of the martyr's intercession for the Church as a whole.⁶⁶ At the execution in *PF*, the spectators are moved by the tremendous love 'fratribus' for their bishop,⁶⁷ and some, 'ex fraterna caritate', offer him wine.⁶⁸ After the martyrdom, 'frates nostri Babylas et Mygdonius',⁶⁹ who are apparently the first ones to have a vision of the ascending martyrs, become a single anonym in Prudentius' account. In *Peristephanon* the word fratres only occurs twice, once in regard to the martyred trio,⁷⁰ and once of their collective devotees.⁷¹ While *PF* preserves significant, named parts for the family members of the local church, Prudentius ultimately changes out the drama's supporting cast for anonymous devotees vying after the favors and services of their cultic heroes: 'certant officiis pii sodales'.⁷²

Finally, regarding the cult of the martyrs,⁷³ Prudentius shifts the focus from the martyred bishop as a local and beloved model of imitation and encouragement during a time of persecution,

⁶⁵ Aemilianus is 'fratrum nostrum': *PF*, ii.1. Felix is 'frater noster': *ibid.* iii.5. Augustalis is 'lector eiusdem': *ibid.* iii.4.

⁶⁶ *Peristephanon*, vi. line 29 does not even mention a recipient of baptism, only its performance. *Peristephanon*, vi. line 75 turns Augustalis and Felix into a vague 'unus', to whose combined request Fructuosus responds negatively, perhaps even critically, 'cur vestri memor ut fiam rogatis?': *Peristephanon*, vi. line 83.

⁶⁷ *PF*, iii.1.

⁶⁸ *Ibid.* iii.2.

⁶⁹ Or Babylon, the more difficult reading for which Jan den Boeft and Jan Bremmer argue, following P. Franchi de' Cavalieri: 'Notiunculae martyrologicae', 51. Ruinart, cited in Boeft and Bremmer, *ibid.* 51, and Musurillo, *Acts*, 182, favor Babylas. The precise name does not sway the argument, that Prudentius makes named characters anonymous.

⁷⁰ 'fratres tergeminos tremunt catastae': *Peristephanon*, vi. line 33.

⁷¹ 'Fratrum tantus amor domum referre / sanctorum cinerum dicata dona / aut gestare sinu fidele pignus': *ibid.* lines 133-5.

⁷² 'companions vie over pious services': *ibid.* line 73.

⁷³ Even the earlier text has ample evidence of a strong martyr-cult. Note *PF*, i.4, which calls attention to the sandals of Fructuosus as a martyr-relic. The plea of Felix to secure the martyr's mindful intercession in iii.6 certainly qualifies. Also note vi., lines 2-3, in which Fructuosus appears to order that his remains be brought to one location, after some of them had been taken by over-zealous members of the church. The archeological discovery of a three-naved necropolis and baptismal piscina in Tarragona dating to this period confirms the presence of a late third, early fourth century martyr-cult. It includes an inscription, 'Memoria sanctorum Fructuosi, Augurii et Eulogii': see Palmer, *Prudentius*, 269-70. Prudentius echoes the same concern for the common and centralized placement of relics, but embellishes by having all three martyrs appear

placing it instead on the bishop as a heroic leader and teacher, and on the three together as co-equal and universal objects of devotion as heavenly patrons and saviours. In *PF*, after his death the martyred bishop appears alone so as to provide a ‘parvulis...exemplum’⁷⁴ and ‘comprobare’⁷⁵ his blessed vindication by God, encouraging other Christians to stand firm in faith against the looming tide of persecution. In *Peristephanon*, however, the motif of the local imitation of the martyr disappears entirely. The bishop’s encouragement is directed at his deacons, not his flock. As their ‘dux et praevis et magister’⁷⁶ and ‘praeceptor’,⁷⁷ he alleviates their fear and ignites their faith.⁷⁸ After this scene, Prudentius seeks to re-focus the drama so that the unique role of Fructuosus is subsumed by the co-equality of the two deacons with their bishop. Prudentius takes poetic pains to make all three occupants of the Tarragonian shrine equal: ‘reddamus paribus pares camenas’.⁷⁹ In keeping with early Christian exegesis of the Danielic story of the three in the fire, both accounts point to the three as a reflection of the Trinity. Yet Prudentius apparently uses the martyred threesome to reinforce the pro-Nicene and anti-Eunomian Orthodoxy of Rome.⁸⁰ Conversely, this Orthodox Trinitarian imagery helps

not only for the purpose of staunching the private disbursement of relics but also to establish their shrine: vi. lines 130-41. In other words, *Peristephanon* has the threesome play a coordinated administrative role in the formation of their own cult and shrine.

⁷⁴ *PF*, vi.2, echoing the common motif of the imitatio Socrati across Christian martyria: cf. *Martyrdom of Apollonius* xxxix-xli; *Pionius* xvii.2-4.

⁷⁵ *PF*, vi.3.

⁷⁶ *Peristephanon* vi, line 10.

⁷⁷ *Ibid.* line 20.

⁷⁸ Fructuosus is worried ‘ne quis socios timor feriret’: *ibid.* line 19. He then gives a heroic summons, ‘indenditque fidem calore Christi’: *ibid.* line 21.

⁷⁹ ‘[L]et us pay back equal poems to the equal ones’: *ibid.* line 153.

⁸⁰ The Roman synod of 368 sought to promulgate broadly Damasus’ pro-Nicene, anti-Arian position, and his insistence on agreement with Rome as the touchstone of Orthodoxy found its way into Theodosius’ *Cunctos populos* in 380. The Roman synod of 382 added to Rome’s official list of errors, a list perhaps authored by Ambrose of Milan. This now included the teachings of Sabellius, Eunomius and the Macedonians, apparently showing basic agreement with Constantinople’s novel formulation regarding the Spirit, while still presuming that event as an Eastern decision that was measured by Rome’s Orthodoxy, not vice versa. See Karl Baus, et al, *The imperial church from Constantine to the early middle ages*, trans. Anselm Biggs, New York, 250-2. It was Ambrose, more than Pope Siricius (384-399), who continued the legacy of Damasus: see Baus, 254. While Prudentius’ poetry lacks specificity in its description of heretical views, his most dogmatic text, the *Apotheosis*, focuses significantly on refuting the errors of Arius and Sabellius, stressing the co-equality and co-existence of Son with Father: see line 255, ‘nec enim minor aut Patre dispar’, and lines 272-3, ‘sed nec decius Pater est, ut pars Patris esset / Filius’. This locates Prudentius in the broad wake of the pro-Nicene theology of

sacralise the cult of the martyrs even further. Besides this, the three are now pictured in *Peristephanon* as patroni⁸¹ and salvatores who protect their (and the author's) native province of Tarraconensis and save their devotees across the world, both now and at the time of destruction in the final judgement.⁸² The motif of universal patronage and pilgrimage furnishes a dramatic inclusio for the entire hymn, subtle at the outset and overt at the crescendo.

In regard to matters of martyr cult, there are also two noteworthy instances of omission. In *PF*, the deacon Augurius also is questioned by the proconsul Aemilianus, who prohibits the deacon from 'heeding the words of Fructuosus'.⁸³ After Augurius responds with a standard confession of monolatry, the proconsul asks, 'Numquid et tu Fructuosum colis'?⁸⁴ Augurius denies the charge, but asserts that he and Fructuosus worship the same God.⁸⁵ In his *Sermo cclxxiii*, while preaching on the martyrdom of Fructuosus, Augustine takes special note of this dialogue. He uses it to highlight the distinction between the worship of God and devotion to the saints.⁸⁶ Prudentius, however, omits it altogether, perhaps finding this exchange unsuited to a poem designed to augment the cult of the bishop Fructuosus, as well as the co-equal status of Augurius.

Damasus and Ambrose, connected to the East but perhaps more sensitive to Arianism as a live threat in the 380s and after by virtue of Justina's presence as well as the nearby Goths.

⁸¹ *Peristephanon*, vi. lines 145-7, where the three are identified as the 'tribus patronis...quorum praesidio fovemur omnes / terrarum populi Pyrenearum', 'the three patrons...under whose protection are kept safe all / the people of the Pyrenean lands'. Roberts notes that the use of 'patronus' for martyrs was a fairly recent development, starting with Ambrose in his *Homilies on Luke*, AD 378: x.12, CSEL xxxii.4.460; then his letter to his sister Marcellina regarding the discovery of the remains of Protasius and Gervasius: *Epistles* lxxvii(xxii), CSEL lxxxii.3.132; xi, CSEL lxxxii.3.119-20. It was quickly picked up by Ambrose's biographer, Paulinus of Nola, whose poetry may well have directly influenced Prudentius at this point. See Roberts, *Poetry*, 21. This suggests that Prudentius' work complemented, even extended that of Ambrose and his circle, rather than working contrary to it; contra Malamud, *Poetics*, 92.

⁸² John Petruccione, 'The martyr death as sacrifice: Prudentius, *Peristephanon* 4, 9-72', *Vigiliae Christianae* xlix (1995), 250, sees in *Peristephanon*, iv. the martyrs playing the role of co-redeemers with Christ, not only in the foundation of the local church but also in the final salvation at the Last Judgement. This is echoed at the very end of *Peristephanon*, vi. His initial plea is for the final salvation of the people of the region at the judgement. 'olim tempus erit ruente mundo / cum te, Tarraco, Fructuosus acri / solvet supplicio tegens ab igni': lines 157-9. At last he beseeches the martyrs for himself, 'meis medellam / formentis dare prosperante Christo': lines 160-2.

⁸³ 'noli verba auscultare': *PF*, ii.6.

⁸⁴ *Ibid.* ii.7.

⁸⁵ *Ibid.* ii.8.

⁸⁶ Augustine, *Sermo cclxxiii*.3.

One other omission may be significant. It consists in the absence of any mention of emperor worship in Prudentius' account. In *PF* Aemilianus expressly ties the worship of the Roman gods to the worship of the 'images of the emperor'.⁸⁷ This may provide an explanation as to why the proconsul Aemilianus questions the deacon Augurius about whether he worships Fructuosus. In the proconsul's mind, apparently, the emperor and bishop are potentially competing objects of worship and so also of political devotion. Though emperor worship might have played well in Prudentius' portrayal of imperial hubris, he opts to omit it.

In the way of drawing conclusions, how may we summarise and make sense of the abundant changes in the martyr story of Fructuosus from *PF* to *Peristephanon*? Literary technique and embellishment certainly play a role in much of the colorful elaboration. As any classical poet, Prudentius dramatises events, engages in word play, and offers learned homages to his poetic predecessors at every opportunity.⁸⁸ The differences may also be ascribed to his audience, a readership already familiar with his source, to the metrical difficulties of names,⁸⁹ or a concern to avoid redundancy. However, the recurring de-historisation and preference for a different vocabulary lends an affect far more than merely literary. Prudentius picks up and deploys mythological and even theological and political perspectives and presuppositions from the beautiful letters and now fits these into a Christian triumphalist program. So what are the theological-political implications of the embellishments and differences previously analyzed?

Since for Prudentius vice is the real culprit, not the empire as such, it becomes clear that *Peristephanon* actually stands within the theological framework of his more popular *Psychomachia*. The martyr stories reflect a cosmic battle happening not essentially between Church and Empire as two Kingdoms, or even two societies or cultures, but rather between virtue and vice in their manifold forms. The characters in the martyr dramas thus become embodiments of virtue or vice, and each martyrdom reveals a triumph for good. The numerous literary parallels between *Psychomachia* and *Peristephanon* point to this as an intentional project.⁹⁰

⁸⁷ 'Hi audiuntur, hi timentur, hi adorantur; si dii non coluntur, nec imperatorum vultus adorantur': *ibid.* ii.6.

⁸⁸ Throughout his literary corpus Prudentius frequently alludes to Vergil, Juvenal, Seneca, Lucan, Statius, and Claudian. For a full summary of allusions see Palmer, *Prudentius*, ch vi.

⁸⁹ For example, in *Peristephanon*, iv. line 163 the poet intentionally strays from the Sapphic metre to accommodate the names of the eighteen; he acknowledges the knowing slip in 165-6. See Thomson, LCL cccxcviii.167 n. a.

⁹⁰ Roberts, *Poetry*, 44ff., convincingly contends that Prudentius follows a consistent sequence of contest and victory throughout *Peristephanon*, the very same plot repeated throughout the *Psychomachia*. Even the sequence of a verbal then physical battle runs repetitively through both texts. This broad based narrative parallel is complemented by connections of

Regarding political ideology, this reframing of the battle suggests that the Roman Empire is not evil *qua* empire, but only in so far as its leaders are ruled by the demonic forces of vice.⁹¹ One may thus imagine the empire working for good if and when the leadership refrains from hubris and polytheism and submits to the one true God. The absence of the issue of emperor worship seems to contribute to this potentially positive appraisal of the role of the empire and its leadership. It also would seem to call into question civil disobedience as a legitimate expression of Christian piety, as it apparently was in *PF*⁹² The principle behind Aemilianus' inquisition in *Peristephanon* actually fits the Orthodox poet living in the wake of *Cunctos populos*: 'quod princeps colit, ut colamus omnes'.⁹³

Turning the martyrs into heroes involves something greater than mere entertainment. New heroes augur a new Rome. Just as Aeneas endured many challenges in order to establish the Roman people, so the heroes of the faith now face enormous struggles in order to establish a new Christian-Roman empire.⁹⁴ This explains why the martyr-heroes must play their script, as it

theme, imagery and word-choice. The battle between Fides and Veterum Cultura Deorum is reflected in the extended back and forth of Romanus and Asclepiades in *Peristephanon*, x. The madness of the persecutors (see above) finds an analogy in the battle between Mens Humilis and Superbia, which falls victim to madness: *Psychomachia*, line 203. The fight between Pudicitia and Sodomita Libido has a concrete example in the contrast between the governor and his virgin daughter here in *Peristephanon*, vi.: see above. Most poignant is the parallel between the martyr-dramas and the battle of Patientia and Ira. The former 'quieta manet' to win victory, and Anger's spear bounces off harmlessly: *Psychomachia*, lines 128ff. So Romanus overcomes his enraged torturers as a 'quietus heros': *Peristephanon*, x. lines 455-6. Here, Fructuosus responds to the official's taunt as a 'placidus... sacerdos': *Peristephanon*, vi. line 43.

⁹¹ Robert Grant sees a similar characterisation of vice in the *Historia ecclesiastica* of Eusebius, which has the effect of vindicating the legitimate Christian rule of Constantine and his followers: see 'Eusebius and imperial propaganda', *Eusebius, Christianity, and Judaism*, Detroit 1992, 665.

⁹² Everett Ferguson brings out this nuance of the significance of martyrdom in his article, 'Early Christian martyrdom and civil disobedience' *Journal of Early Christian Studies* i (1993), 73-83. Defiance of the 'imperial decrees' and the summons to emperor worship 'made Christians guilty of civil disobedience, or even of treason': *ibid.* 80.

⁹³ *Peristephanon*, vi. line 42.

⁹⁴ *Peristephanon*, vi. does not deal with this as does the story of Lawrence: see *Peristephanon*, ii. lines 1-4, 410-11, 432-5, 443-4, 469-72. Yet, it is still a part of his all-encompassing narrative of the conversion of Rome, so that Rome 'can now be seen as the head of an empire, founded providentially by Christ for the promotion of universal conversion': Palmer, *Prudentius*, 122. Wilken also notes this in his discussion of *Peristephanon*, ii.: *Spirit*, 224. Rome's martyr-cult centrality is evidenced by the proportion of verses given to Rome-

were, in an epic battle, even conquest. The recurrent narrative script, together with the extended focus on military martyrs, suggests that the whole collection may be read as a dramatic albeit predictable agon. On stage are the exercitus Christi and the exercitus Caesaris,⁹⁵ or more precisely, the exercitus recti and exercitus viti. The Orthodox triumph vicariously in the martyr-contests of their forebears.

Prudentius' numerous highlights of martyr cultus hold theological and political import as well. The bishop is no longer the central figure around which the church as family is bound together, and his message no longer one of comfort and hope during a time of persecution. Rather, the Church as Distinct Family is replaced by the Church as Roman Society. The martyred threesome together now belong to the cities and regions of their birth or death or both, and so also to the whole of the newly Christian-Roman society. As ever-present patroni of their cities they together form a heavenly army to defend the now Christian Empire. The faithful masses take pious pride in their local martyrs as they pay homage to distant ones in pilgrimage. The burgeoning cult of the martyrs and accompanying exchange of pilgrims between Rome, Spain, Gaul, and Africa serve to unify the Church as Empire.⁹⁶

The sum effect is to meld religious devotion and patriotism,⁹⁷ quite in keeping with Rome's long history of sponsoring polylatry. It was precisely this ideological union that stood as one of the major causes of Christian martyrdom previously.⁹⁸ Ironically, the poet who sought to elevate his

affiliated martyrs in *Peristephanon*—2275 out of 3763 verses, or 60%, by my calculation—as well as by the fact that the two longest hymns, x and ii, are thoroughly preoccupied with the narrative of Rome's conversion. The *Apotheosis* actually yields the theological background for this idea. There Prudentius avers that the Incarnation itself brought about the effective end of polytheistic religion, 435-43, throwing the constellations into disarray, 617-26, inevitably leading to the heir of Aeneas worshipping in Christ's basilica, 446-8. All of this bespeaks the success of the vision of Damasus and his successors to promote Rome's mythic status as the ultimate pilgrimage center in the West and beyond.

⁹⁵ Palmer, *Prudentius*, 142-3.

⁹⁶ See the image of the martyr-pyre as a pilgrim-guiding lighthouse in *Peristephanon*, vi. line 3. See especially *Peristephanon*, iv. lines 5-52, which elaborates a massive exchange of martyr relics between Carthage, Corduba, Tarraco, Gerunda, Calagurris, Barchinon, Narbo, Arelas, Emerita, Complutum, and Tingis.

⁹⁷ Palmer, *Prudentius*, 4, 123. 'The martyr becomes the embodiment not simply of religious faith but also of civic devotion, even of patriotism in the new Christian and Roman civitas': Wilken, *Spirit*, 226.

⁹⁸ Martyrs such as Polycarp fundamentally challenged this union, 'He and the host of faithful witnesses before and after him gave a testimony to the supreme claims of God and the limitations of the State... [T]he early Christian witness was an important step in desacralizing the State': Ferguson, 'Early Christian martyrdom', 83.

beloved martyrs underwrote the ideology that made new ones.⁹⁹ And somehow, in view of the looming fall of a city and much of an empire, the more ancient and course report seems more prophetic than its muse-inspired counterpart.¹⁰⁰

⁹⁹ See Maureen A. Tilley, *Donatist martyr stories*, Liverpool 1996, xxiii-xxiv, in which the author even claims that ‘the union of state and religion intensified’ with the Constantinian settlement, while noting the inseparability of religious and imperial duty in the person of the emperor.

¹⁰⁰ Prudentius even invokes Romanus as muse, foreshadowing the cutting out of the martyr’s tongue and miraculous subsequent speech, ‘Romane... / elinguis oris organum fautor move, / largire comptum carmen infantissimo’: *Peristephanon*, x. lines 1-3.